

Bridging the gap between knowledge and application, between research and industry, to transform talent into sustainable and competitive innovation

Best practice category

Skills, Research Collaboration

Stakeholder group

Research and Academia

Value chain position

R&D

General Information

The Politecnico di Milano is among the best European universities, a reference point for **engineering, technology** and **design**. An important strength is its approach towards applied research and technology transfer. In practice, its mission combines high-level study, targeted training, and partnerships with companies, thus creating an exceptional environment for innovation. Politecnico recognises that the ability to innovate and produce semiconductors in Europe is crucial and it promotes robust partnerships between universities and industry, offering advanced laboratories, infrastructure, and training programs involving students, PhD students, and researchers. Among the courses of excellence are: the Master's Degree in Electronics Engineering with specialisations in **analog/digital integrated circuits, power electronics, microcontrollers, and FPGAs**; the EIT Digital Major in Embedded Systems Design (Intelligent Chips and Systems), a new double degree within the Master's Degree in Computer Science and Engineering, and the Track in Micro and Nano Systems, which allows students to study materials, engineering physics, or mechanical engineering applied to micro and nanosystems in depth.

Activities and best practices

- One of the key strengths of Politecnico di Milano is its ability to forge strategic collaborations with leading industrial partners. A prime example is the partnership with Infineon. In 2025 was announced a strategic expansion of the initial Joint Research Center established in 2019, which has now evolved into the broader Joint Research Platform. This platform is an important hub that brings together interdisciplinary research groups. There is a focus on cutting-edge topics such as **radio frequency (RF) hardware, sensor systems, AI-supported algorithms, and system prototyping for critical applications**, such as driver assistance, connectivity, and safety technologies. The benefit is twofold: students and doctoral candidates gain invaluable practical experience in state-of-the-art laboratories and Infineon benefits from direct access to specialised talent. In recent years, this synergy has already led to tangible results: specific products have been developed and patents have been registered in close collaboration with PhD graduates. With the further strengthening of the partnership between Infineon and the Politecnico, the goal is to train and place up to 20 PhD students in various research projects in the coming cycles.

- The Politecnico di Milano, through its Department of **Mechanical Engineering**, also plays a strategic role in the GENESIS (GENerate in Europe a Sustainable Industry for Semiconductors) project, launched in 2025, and coordinated by **CEA-Leti**. The aim of the project is to transform the European semiconductor supply chain in a sustainable way, through the promotion of eco-friendly materials, advanced monitoring of production processes, waste minimisation, and management of **critical raw materials**. As part of the project, the Politecnico is developing **artificial intelligence models** to monitor and optimise **PFAS emissions** in production processes, improving sensor accuracy and proactive management of environmental and health risks. It also allows for collaboration at the national level, the project coordinated by the Politecnico includes the **University of Catania**, the **University of Rome Tor Vergata**, **Leonardo**, and leading companies such as **STMicroelectronics**.
- Through its PoliFAB micro and nanotechnology infrastructure, the Politecnico di Milano has been collaborating with **STMicroelectronics** since 2016 on research and development in **MEMS, motion control, power electronics, galvanic isolation**, and **sensor systems** using advanced materials. The five-year expansion of the partnership in 2021 has enabled PoliFAB to be equipped with **clean rooms** and state-of-the-art instrumentation. This scenario has created an ideal environment for experimentation and innovation in the fields of microelectronics and nanoelectronics, as well as photonics, biotechnology and advanced materials.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Innovation and the production of critical technologies in Europe require interdisciplinary skills, and strong collaboration between industry and academia. Politecnico addresses this challenge thanks to a strong network and strategic partnerships with industry giants such as Infineon and STMicroelectronics. This model helps to bridge the European skills gap by training a new generation of students, PhD students, and researchers in essential fields: from microelectronics to MEMS, from advanced sensor technology to artificial intelligence applied to embedded systems and production processes. In addition, the Politecnico leads the way in adopting responsible practices. European projects such as GENESIS are pushing towards sustainable semiconductor production, focusing on eco-friendly materials, waste reduction, and strategic management of raw materials. These initiatives strengthen our position in the world, because it gives us both the necessary skills and the guarantee of having cutting-edge and responsible industrial standards.